

Inflammatory Markers and the Metabolic Syndrome in Pakistan

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript

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ABSTRACT

The metabolic disorder has been conceptualized as a bunching of metabolic syndrome, including insulin obstruction, dyslipidemia, focal adiposity, and raised circulatory strain (BP) that increment risk for cardiovascular infection (CVD) and type 2 diabetes. The main objective of the study is to analyse the relationship between inflammatory markers and the metabolic syndrome In Pakistani population. This descriptive study was conducted in Sheikh Zayed Hospital RYK during July 2021 to December 2021. This study was finished with the consent of moral board of emergency clinic. The information was gathered from 150 patients of the two sexual orientations. The information was gathered from 150 patients from which 50 females and 100 males. In the second gathering C-receptive protein is higher than in the principal bunch with measurable importance ($p = 0.02$). Leukocytes have a less significant worth in laying out proinflammatory and cardiovascular gamble commitment in patients with metabolic disorder contrasted and C-responsive protein. It is presumed that corpulence is the principle element of metabolic condition. Patients determined to have metabolic condition present an enacted fiery status. Provocative disorder is communicated by the quantity of metabolic condition parts.

Keywords: *Metabolic syndrome; obesity; hypertension; hyperglycemia; inflammatory markers.*

1. INTRODUCTION

“The metabolic syndrome has been conceptualized as a clustering of metabolic risk factors, including insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, central adiposity, and elevated blood pressure (BP) that increase risk for cardiovascular disease (CVD) and type 2 diabetes. These risk factors covary in epidemiological investigations and, when combined, predict incident disease, disease course, and mortality, with the aggregate syndrome accounting for cardiovascular risk beyond that associated with the component risk factors” [1].

“The clinical definition of metabolic syndrome has undergone several iterations. The current guidelines promulgated by the American Heart Association and the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute largely overlap with those recommended by the International Diabetes Federation and require evidence of three of the following five criteria: elevated fasting glucose, elevated BP, large waist circumference “[2], “elevated triglycerides and reduced high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol. Recently, it has also been proposed that markers of systemic inflammation be included in the definition of the syndrome” [3]. “In this regard, elevated peripheral levels of proinflammatory mediators, such as C-reactive protein (CRP) and interleukin (IL)-6, correlate with individual components of the metabolic syndrome and confer cardiovascular and metabolic risk beyond that associated with the clinically defined syndrome” [4]. “Furthermore, mounting evidence suggests that inflammation plays a causal role in the development of both obesity and insulin resistance and may provide a common link between established components of the syndrome” [5].

“The Metabolic Syndrome (MS) is associated with a systemic inflammatory response that plays an important pathogenetic role in atherothrombotic disease. Highly sensitive C-reactive protein (hsCRP) and fibrinogen are acute phase reactants and indicate underlying inflammatory state. PAI-1 is a pro-inflammatory adipokine with pro-thrombotic effects that is also increased in obesity, including children and adolescents when compared with a control group” [6]. “Some studies have reported an association between PAI-1 and the prevalence of MetS, including adolescents” [7].

“Increasing evidence suggests that chronic, low-grade inflammation may be a common symptom

involving the pathogenesis of MetS and cardiovascular disease. The contribution of the MetS to atherosclerosis may be related to its chronic inflammatory and thrombotic status” [8]. “A proinflammatory state, as indicated by increased circulating TNF- α and high-sensitivity C-reactive protein levels, and a prothrombotic state, evidenced by increased PAI-1 levels, are often observed in MetS patients. Other studies demonstrated that high-sensitivity C-reactive protein is an independent predictor for myocardial infarction, stroke, peripheral artery disease and sudden cardiac death. In addition, an elevated PAI-1 level was a predictor of the occurrence of myocardial infarction” [9].

2. OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the study is to analyse the relationship between inflammatory markers and the metabolic syndrome in Pakistani population.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This descriptive study was conducted in Sheikh Zayed hospital RYK during July 2021 to December 2021. This study was finished with the consent of moral board of emergency clinic. The information was gathered from 150 patients of the two sexual orientations. The review bunches were isolated into three principle parts.

1. Abdominal obesity+arterial hypertension + hyperglycemia
2. Abdominal stoutness + arterial hypertension + hyperglycemia+decreased high thickness lipoprotein+increased fatty oils
3. Control group

3.1 Biochemical Examination

The blood was drawn from all patients for additional examination of incendiary markers. Blood was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes and serum was isolated. Blood tests were gathered into EDTA tubes. Hence, indomethacin and butylate dhydroxy toluene were added into the plasma tests. Blood tests were put away at - 80°C. Each tests was rehashed multiple times and information were shown as mean $\pm$ SD and broke down through SPSS 22.0 (IBM, USA). Understudy t-test was applied for brings about two gatherings and one-way ANOVA was for results more than two. P<0.05 was considered to have critical significance.

4. RESULTS

The information was gathered from 150 patients from which 50 females and 100 males. In the second gathering C-receptive protein is higher than in the principal bunch with measurable importance ($p = 0.02$). Leukocytes have a less significant worth in laying out pro inflammatory and cardiovascular gamble commitment in patients with metabolic disorder contrasted and C-responsive protein.

Compared to normal cell line, EIF3K expressed lower in inflammatory cell line. Furthermore, over expressed IEF3K could up-regulate expression of EIF3K in inflammatory cell line and suppressed cell viabilities. Apoptosis and autophagy were detected as well, which indicated that expression of Bcl-2 was inhibited and expressions of Bax and caspase-3 were promoted. In autophagy, expression of LC3- II was up-regulated and LC3- I and p62 were suppressed.

Table 1. Leukocytes and CPR values

	CRP (mg/dl)	Leukocytes (μ l)
First group	0.79 $\pm$ 0.8	12600 $\pm$ 1000
Second group	0.9 $\pm$ 0.8	14100 $\pm$ 1000
P	0.02	0.07

Fig. 1. Circular EIF3K expressed lower in inflammatory cells of oviduct and promoted apoptosis and autophagy

5. DISCUSSION

“Pro-inflammatory mechanisms can be considered as a base of increased cardiovascular risk. Proinflammatory activity is more significant if metabolic syndrome is characterised by more elements. The results we obtained ascertain that inflammatory status is increased in patients diagnosed with metabolic syndrome (significantly statistic in subjects that associate more than 3 elements). Inflammatory injury has different severity depending on the elements that define metabolic syndrome and on their association. Once the inflammation level increases there is a differentiated prognostic impact for cardiovascular events” [9,10].

“Metabolic syndrome frequency is progressively increasing and evaluation of proinflammatory risk of this entity is valuable, as assesment of some inflammatory biomarkers implies minimum costs and it can be repeated” [11]. “In our study CRP proved to be an accurate indicator of inflammation for patients with metabolic syndrome. In subjects with acute coronary syndrome, stroke, periferic vascular disease and sudden death, recent epidemiological data ascertained a positive association between CRP levels and clinic manifestations of atherothrombosis” [12]. “Increased values of CRP represent a predictive marker for unfavourable evolution in patients with unstable angina pectoris after myocardial revascularisation, as well as in patients with metabolic syndrome and diabetes – that suggests its role in atherogenesis” [13-15].

6. CONCLUSION

It is concluded that corpulence is the principle element of metabolic condition. Patients determined to have metabolic condition present an enacted fiery status. Provocative disorder is communicated by the quantity of metabolic condition parts.

DISCLAIMER

The products used for this research are commonly and predominantly use products in our area of research and country. There is absolutely no conflict of interest between the authors and producers of the products because we do not intend to use these products as an avenue for any litigation but for the advancement of knowledge. Also, the research was not funded by

the producing company rather it was funded by personal efforts of the authors.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

As per international standard or university standard written ethical approval has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

CONSENT

As per international standard or university standard, patients' written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Han TS, Sattar N, Williams K, et al. Prospective study of C-reactive protein in relation to the development of diabetes and metabolic syndrome in the Mexico City Diabetes Study. *Diabetes Care*. 2002;25:2016-2021.
2. Lee YH, Pratley RE. The evolving role of inflammation in obesity and the metabolic syndrome. *Current Diabetes Reports*. 2005;5:70-75.
3. Rana JS, Nieuwdorp M, Jukema JW, et al. Cardiovascular metabolic syndrome - an interplay of, obesity, inflammation, diabetes and coronary heart disease. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2007;9:218-232.
4. McCaffery JM, Shen BJ, Muldoon MF, et al. Ambulatory blood pressure and the metabolic syndrome in normotensive and untreated hypertensive men. *Metab Syndr Relat Disord*. 2007;5:34-44.
5. Shen BJ, Todaro JF, Niaura R, et al. Are metabolic risk factors one unified syndrome? Modeling the structure of the metabolic syndrome X. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2003;157:701-711.
6. Shen BJ, Goldberg RB, Llabre MM, et al. Is the factor structure of the metabolic syndrome comparable between men and women and across three ethnic groups: the Miami Community Health Study. *Ann Epidemiol*. 2006;16:131-137.
7. Bentler PM, Weeks DG. Linear structural equations with latent variables. *Psychometrika*. 1980;45:289-308.

8. Bentler PM. EQS structural equations program manual. Encino, CA: Multivariate Software; 1995.
9. Piche ME, Lemieux S, Weisnagel SJ, et al. Relation of high-sensitivity C-reactive protein, interleukin-6, tumor necrosis factor-alpha, and fibrinogen to abdominal adipose tissue, blood pressure, and cholesterol and triglyceride levels in healthy postmenopausal women. *Am J Cardiol.* 2005;96:92-97.
10. Ridker PM, Brown NJ, Vaughan DE, et al. Established and emerging plasma biomarkers in the prediction of first atherothrombotic events. *Circulation.* 2004;109:IV6-IV19.
11. Ridker PM, Buring JE, Cook NR, et al. C-reactive protein, the metabolic syndrome, and risk of incident cardiovascular events: an 8-year follow-up of 14,719 initially healthy American women. *Circulation.* 2003;107:391-397.
12. Sattar N, Gaw A, Scherbakova O, et al. Metabolic syndrome with and without C-reactive protein as a predictor of coronary heart disease and diabetes in the West of Scotland Coronary Prevention Study. *Circulation.* 2003;108:414-419.
13. Yudkin JS, Stehouwer CD, Emeis JJ, et al. C-reactive protein in healthy subjects: associations with obesity, insulin resistance, and endothelial dysfunction: a potential role for cytokines originating from adipose tissue? *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol.* 1999;19:972-978.

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